

Contemporary Educational Issues in Girls' Colleges of Rural Haryana: A Study

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ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this paper is to review the contemporary challenges in Girls' colleges of rural Haryana and the role of government, leaders, parents, teachers and the students for sustainable educational development in these colleges. There are many challenges in today's educational system. Apart from the old shortcomings, the new challenges have been added after Covid-19 pandemic. Despite of progress in educational system, it no longer keeps pace with the need of rural girl students. In the paper several issues- number of students; dropouts; Absenteeism; lack of funding; shortage of teachers, administrative staff and resources; health and safety of girl students; negative effects of technology; and poverty- are analyzed. Analysis suggests the corrective measures how teaching in rural girls' colleges of Haryana can sustain during and after Covid-19. The paper suggests that Government, political leaders, parents, teachers and students should work together and prioritize educational reforms for meeting the required need.

KEY WORDS: Women's education, Challenges, Dropouts, Poverty, Rural students

INTRODUCTION:

Women's education is foremost important medium for progress of a society. An educated man can be a medium for progress of one family but an educated woman can be a medium for progress of two families. Education brings an all round development in a woman. It brings enlightenment and eradicates darkness of bad customs, superstitions and outworn rituals. Keeping educated women's role in development of the nation, the Government of India has formulated various educational programs to enhance women's

education in the country. And these policies and programs have brought the significant positive change in women's education in India in general and in Haryana in particular. The data of All India Survey of Higher Education (AISHE) report shows that in Haryana the strength of the girl students have surpassed the boys' in pursuing higher education. According to AISHE report the total enrolment in higher education institutes in Haryana in 2019-20 was 9.33 lacs students. And out of this the strength of girl students was 4.73 lacs (13 lacs more) as compared to 4.60 lacs boys students. Apart from this, the strength of female teachers (20690) also has surpassed the strength of male teachers (18541) in higher education institutes in Haryana.

But, despite of progress in girls' education in Haryana, there have always been many challenges for education in girls' colleges of rural Haryana. Apart from old shortcomings – number of students; lack of funding, teachers, administrative staff and resources etc.; health and safety of girl students; illiteracy of parents and poverty- the pandemic, Covid-19 has added many new challenges for education in the girls' colleges of rural Haryana. It has posited the challenge- how teaching can sustain during and even after Covid; challenge to adapt new standards for both- teachers and students. Online teaching enabled a teacher to teach many students at a time, irrespective of geographic distance; recorded lectures on MOOCs enabled students to take their lectures at any time of their convenience without going to college. It posited the challenge to survive for many teachers and also it posited challenge of keeping the study continue for the rural students as they could not adapt the new standards; many of them are not in access of new technology i.e. internet, gadgets etc.

SEVERAL ISSUES:

Students' Dropout: The girls' colleges of rural Haryana face a big challenge of maintaining the strength of students. Many students get married between the course and some of them drop their study soon after marriage while some others drop after sometime when they come into family way. As per the data of the office of Registrar Government College for Women Pali, Rewari (a girls' college of rural Haryana), there is a significant ratio of dropout students from their admission in 1st year to their completion of course in 3rd year. In batch 2019-20, the total number of students in all the streams in 1st year was 157, in 2nd year the strength was declined and the total number was 151, and in the final year the strength was further declined and the total strength of the students in all the three streams was left only 137. In batch 2020-21, the total number of students in all the streams in 1st year was 163, in 2nd year the strength was declined and the total number

was 158, and in the final year the strength was further declined and the total strength of the students in all the three streams was left only 156. In batch 2021-22, the total number of students in all the streams in 1st year was 161, in 2nd year the strength was declined and the total number was 151, and in the final year the strength was further declined and the total strength of the students in all the three streams was left only 145.

After the analysis of above data of consecutive three batches we find that strength of the students is on decline significantly in every consecutive year i.e. from first year to final year. This decline in students' strength is because of many students get married just after their admission in first year in college or at most they reach in their 2nd year and some of them drop their study soon after marriage while some others drop after sometime (up to final year) when they come into family way.

Lack of Funding: Lack of funding has always been an issue with girls' colleges of rural Haryana. Girls colleges need more funds as compare to boys colleges as comparatively more money is needed for security of the girls students, also more money is needed for proper hygiene of girl students. Lack of fund to maintain hygienic facilities become a major reason for absence of girl students. In a survey, conducted on 27 students who were absent on the previous day in GCW Pali (A girls' College of rural Haryana), it was found, from their answers, that out of 27 absent students 04 students did not come to the college as they were on women's problem on the day and there was no proper hygienic provision such as sanitary pads etc. in the college. So, they stayed at home.

Lack of Teachers, Administrative Staff and Resources: although there is a continue shortfall of teachers and administrative staff in most of the educational institutes in India. All the higher education institutes including top ranking IITs are facing a continue faculty shortage. The shortage of faculty is even more in the rural colleges. Not only is the shortage of faculty but also there is acute shortage of administrative staff and other resources in Girls' colleges of rural Haryana. Although, to meet the issue, the Government of Haryana has taken the right step by implementing compulsory 05 years rural service for college faculties yet there are many vacancies of teaching post in girls' colleges of rural Haryana. To make the situation worse the teachers, who are already insufficient in number to cater academic requirements of the students, are overburdened of non-academic and administrative tasks. Due to lack of administrative staff in rural colleges a teacher has to do all the works starting from a clerk to an administrator. The teacher is forced to curtail his teaching time to complete his non-academic tasks. It puts very negative effects on teaching learning process.

Besides, the teachers are ordered very frequently by District Administration to perform various duties. During Covid-19 the college teachers were performing as Duty Magistrates. They were deployed to control their assigned sectors. They performed their duty working in two shifts i.e. in the manner of 12 hrs duty and 12 hrs rest. Out of their rest time they had to prepare their lectures and also they had to give online classes to their students. They became so much overburdened that many of them went under stress. And it is to note that a teacher, if s/he is under stress, s/he can never give his/her best to the students.

Health and Safety of Students: After Covid-19 pandemic Health and safety is one of the major issues in girl's colleges. In girls colleges health issues are more as compared to boys' colleges. Girls naturally need more sanitation and hygienic requirements. Covid-19 has added many more concerns in regard to health and safety. The girls' colleges of rural Haryana who are already forced to cop up with the limited financial grants face a new challenge to implement the safety measures as per the Covid norms.

Challenge to Connect Students in Online Classes: The effects of Covid-19 have been the most in the field of education. It brought a drastic change in education system and standards. The classroom teaching is replaced by virtual classes. It forced sudden changes on the role of teachers and students. The teachers were forced to adapt new ways of teaching; the teachers had to develop the skills of conducting online classes and the students also needed to learn to attend online classes.

During and after Covid Pandemic, sifting of teaching from classroom to virtual classes posited a big challenge for teachers of girls' colleges of rural Haryana. It became very challenging for the teachers of girls' colleges of rural Haryana to connect rural students in virtual classes as, first, there is internet problem in rural area, second, the poor parents of rural area can't afford to provide the facilities for virtual classes i.e. internet services, gadgets and devices to the students, third, the uneducated or less educated parents of girl students don't allow them to use mobile, internet as they fear in case the girls misuse them and fourth, there is no ambience in the society of rural Haryana towards importance of education in general and girls' education is not given importance in rural area.

Misuse of Technology: Although educational technology plays a very important role in modern education system and it is meant to engage students in active learning yet sometimes it becomes distraction for rural students. The girl students of rural area are very curious; they digress from their studies and sneak time to play video games, check

social media, watch reels and other useless contents. The most negative effect of technology on rural students is that they get exposure of alcohol, drugs and other harmful things that make them anxious to taste these forbidden things.

Poverty in Parents: Most of the parents of the students of rural Haryana are poor. They cannot afford proper resources- study material etc. also the poor parents are unable to provide good nutritious foods to these students. The effect of malnutrition on girl students of rural Haryana is that they tend to perform less in their studies and co curricular activities. Because of poverty, the poor girl students experience other family problems also. They are forced to take over the housework and taking care of siblings instead of receiving education. They are married in early age mostly during 1st year or 2nd Year of their Graduation and soon after their marriage they go into family way. it hampers their study by bringing multifold responsibilities for them. Many of these responsibilities become more important than their study hence they shift their mind from study to their family responsibilities. They starts becoming absent from college, miss their classes, do not take their lectures and practical classes, so they fail in the examination and eventually they drop their study.

CONCLUSION:

Girls colleges of rural Haryana face many educational issues. Apart from old longstanding issues, many more new challenges have been posited after Covid-19 pandemic. The pandemic has put very negative effects on teaching learning process in girls' colleges of rural Haryana. It has brought the drastic changes in education from class room teaching to virtual online teaching. The parents of rural Haryana are too poor to provide internet facilities and gadgets for online classes to their wards; parents are uneducated and there is no ambience in society towards importance of girls' education. Thus, it has become very challenging to adopt this new way of teaching for all the colleges of rural areas in general and girls' colleges of rural Haryana in particular. In addition it is very challenging for the teachers to connect a rural girl student in online virtual classes.

Thus, in ultimate analysis, it can be argued that all of the four pillars- the government, the leaders, the parents and the students- need to work together for sustainable development in the girls colleges of rural Haryana. Government should make provisions of granting stipend to the students to purchase the appropriate gadgets to attend online classes. All the vacant posts of the faculty in rural colleges must be filled either by appointment or by

adjustment (deputation) and the teachers must not be overburdened by giving them non-academic task. The political leaders and other renowned personality should work for making ambience of girls' education in the society. Most of the parents of rural Haryana who are poor and uneducated think that a girl child is just a responsibility for them rather they think of her as a burden and, so, they marry her as soon as possible, sometimes, even before she attains her marriageable age. They must change their attitude. They should treat the girls equal to the boys and should give them equal opportunity to excel in life. The parents should marry the girls only after they have completed their academics so that their marriage and family responsibilities must not hamper their study. And the girl students of rural Haryana also need to give top priority to their study. They must know that the technology and internet are meant to engage them in active learning. They should make good use of technology and must not let the technology distract them. They must not sneak their precious time in WhatsApp chatting, in watching reels, in checking social media and in playing video games.

CITATION

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